

Twenty-four single plants falling in the range from $\bar{X} + 1$ SD to $\bar{X} + 2$ SD that also were better than check variety PMK1 in all characters were selected to forward to the F₃.

Metroglyph analysis could identify crosses and plants likely to produce superior progenies in early generations. The technique can be used while excising unidirectional selection in variable populations. □

Index score for different traits.

	Tillers per plant (no.)	Panicle length (cm)	Plant height (cm)	Single-plant yield (g)
Range of means	5.2 - 11.2	17.0 - 23.7	64.8 - 76.8	11.9 - 15.1
Score 1 value <	6.7	18.7	67.8	12.75
Score 2	6.8 - 8.2	18.8 - 20.3	67.8 - 70.8	12.76-13.5
Score 3	8.3 - 9.7	20.4 - 22.0	70.9 - 73.8	13.6 - 14.25
Score 4 value >	9.8	22.1	73.9	14.25
\bar{X}	8.8	21.3	70.03	13.1
X + 1 SD	8.93	23.15	73.23	14.11
SE	0.04	0.56	0.96	0.31
CV (%)	1.5	8.67	4.57	7.7

Anther culturability of rice plants treated with male gametocide chemicals

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We evaluated the callus-forming abilities of anthers derived from F₁ rice plants of the japonica/indica hybrid IRAT13/H105 treated with the chemical hybridization agent G5 at 0.5 and 1.0 g/liter at 2 stages of panicle development (before and after meiosis). G5 is known to be effective on wheat and, to a lesser degree, on rice.

The number of anthers forming calli was three times higher in anthers treated with 1.0 g G5/liter before meiosis than in control (see table). Time of appearance of the first callus also was 6-8 d earlier. However, regenerability of induced calli did not differ significantly from that of the control.

The gametocidal effect of G5 on rice pollen sterility measured just before anthesis increased with increased application but remained weak. Spikelet sterility with 1.0 g G5/liter was 30-40% higher than control.

These results agree with results obtained in wheat.

The same experimental protocol was followed to assess the effect of ethephon at 2 and 4 g/liter on callus-forming abilities of treated anthers. In this case, discrepancies were noted among the results of the three replications. Spraying ethephon on donor plants does not appear to be a reliable way to increase rice anther culturability. □

Scatter diagram of metroglyph analysis using 12 crosses. ACRI, Tamil Nadu, India, 1988. 1-Norungan/MDU1, 2-Charumpuncha/MDU1 (5), 3 - ZR29/PMK1 (7), 4 - Arurakari/IR20 (11), 5 - Moongil samba/IR50 (11), 6 - IR29/IR50 (13), 7 - Charumpuncha/IR50 (9), 8 - MDU1/PMK1 (12), 9 - MDU1/IR50 (12), 10 - Norungan/IR50 (15), 11 - W1263/MDU1 (11), 12 - Moongil samba/MDU1 (8), C - PMK1 (check) (6). Figures in parentheses denote score index values.

Yield potential

Sources of variability in rice seed quality

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An inherent heterogeneity in rice seed quality exists between tillers of a plant and between plants in a population. When a variety is grown in different

Effect of male gametocide chemicals on callus formation ability of rice anthers.

Treatment	Callus-forming ability ^a (%)	
	Before meiosis	After meiosis
Distilled water (control)	5.6 a	5.4 a
0.5 g gametocide/liter	13.1 a	4.9 a
1.0 g gametocide/liter	17.8 b	3.8 a

^aAvof 2 replications, 1000 anthers each treatment. Means followed by a common letter are not significantly different at the 5% level by DMRT.